

The Effects of Perceived Organizational Support and Abusive Supervision on Employee's Turnover Intention: The Mediating Roles of Psychological Contract and Emotional Exhaustion

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Abstract : Workers (especially, competent personnel) have been recognized as a core contributor to overall organizational effectiveness. Hence, verifying the determinants of turnover intention is one of the most important research issues. This study tested the influence of perceived organizational support and abusive supervision on employee's turnover intention. In addition, mediating roles of psychological contract and emotional exhaustion were examined. Data from 255 Korean employees supported all hypotheses Implications for research and directions for future research are discussed.

Keywords : abusive supervision, emotional exhaustion, perceived organizational support, psychological contract, turnover intention

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